

SHIELDING EFFECTS OF DIFFERENT ASPECT RATIO OF ALUMINUM FLAKES IN CONDUCTIVE PLASTICS FOR INJECTION MOLDING PROCESSES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a study of comparing three aspect-ratio conductive plastic composite materials based on acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) compounded with aluminum flakes for the shielding effectiveness of injection molding products against electromagnetic interference (EMI). Aspect ratio (AR) of these conductive plastics is 6, 156 and 695 as well as content is ABS/AL 37wt%, ABS/AL 10.4wt%, and ABS/AL 36wt%, respectively. The EMI values were obtained between 45 dB and 28 dB for AR695 conductive plastics. The relationship of EMI value regarding aspect ratio, conductive network, critical concentration, and gate system of injection mold are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: electromagnetic interference (EMI), aluminum flakes, conductive plastics composite, injection molding

INTRODUCTION

Recent widespread use of electronic devices has increased electromagnetic interference (EMI) problems due to the generation of electromagnetic energy. Electromagnetic wave interference will become an invisible public hazard in the twenty-one century [1,2]. Electromagnetic wave covers wide range of frequencies including radio frequency, TV signal, radar and X-ray [2]. Besides the possible harmfulness to humans, some precise machines including aircraft guidance systems, and medical equipment such as electrocardiograph, pacemakers and related computer systems may be interfered to malfunction [2].

Currently, most of the cabinets of electronic and computer products are manufactured by injection molding processes using engineering plastics, such as ABS and PPO. Since surface resistivity of plastics is $10^{16}\sim 10^{17}$ Ω/Sq , plastics are usually categorized as insulation materials to EMI shielding effectiveness [3]. Plastic materials need to be upgraded its electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness for satisfying the regulations around the world. In general, metal shielding is the traditional way to be adopted because of its good shielding effectiveness. However, the weight of metal shielding is too heavy for making complex shapes and the equipment of treatment of corrosive protection on the surface is expensive to keep products competitive. Thus metallizing plastic cabinets are popular for

meliorating the above imperfection [4]. Generally, conductive plastics are made by adding conductive fibers or flakes in the base resin. The most common fillers are carbon fibers, nickel coated graphite (NCG) fibers, stainless steel fibers, and aluminum fibers or flakes. The amount of fillers in the resin is usually among 7-20 % of the total volume depending upon the level of shielding required [5]. In this research, aluminum flakes are adopted as metallic fillers to be directly combined into polymer to produce conductive plastics composite resin. Some challenges for use of conductive plastic composite materials are listed as follows:

1. Dimensional aspect ratio (AR) of aluminum flakes must be high enough to form conductive network.
2. Volume of aluminum flakes needs to be sufficiently high to form overlap or conductive network.
3. Gating system of injection molding has to be modified for improving distribution of aluminum flakes in ABS polymer.
4. Cluster and distortion of aluminum flake flow in mold interior need to be solved during injection molding.

Different aspect ratio and its filler of weight percent are known to affect EMI shielding effectiveness [6]. The higher aspect ratio of aluminum flakes is in the resin matrix, the easier for aluminum flakes to form overlap or conductive network that provides a continuous conductive path throughout other flakes in plastic [7]. From the viewpoint of cost and shielding effectiveness, injection molding process was used in this research to fabricate products of three aspect-ratio conductive plastic composite materials based on acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene (ABS) compounded with aluminum flakes. Aspect ratio of these conductive plastics is 6, 156, and 695 as well as content is ABS/AL 37wt%, ABS/AL 10.4wt%, and ABS/AL 36wt%, respectively. Relationships between EMI shielding effectiveness and aspect ratio, weight percent, and gate system of injection molding are also investigated for improving the EMI values to meet the industrial demands.

LITERATURE REVIEW

M.T. Kortschot and R.T. Woodhams [6] proposed the characteristics of a conductive filler in terms of efficiency and critical concentration. The concentration of the conductive particles is the overriding factor to determining the composite conductivity, shielding effectiveness, and cost. At the critical concentration, the percolation threshold is reached as network formation commences and then the resistivity decreases greatly. A few weight percentage beyond the critical concentration will invariably produce a composite that has useful conductivity. An “efficient” EMI additive may be defined as one which has a very small critical concentration [8]. Few studies have examined the relationship between critical concentration and parameters such as particle size and shape, or filler dispersion. Davenport [6] compared the critical concentration of conductive fibers of various aspect ratios with their dry packing fractions. A correlation between packing fraction and critical concentration was found and a critical concentration was reported that exceeded the packing fraction for fibers with aspect ratios greater than 100.

Therefore, the most important characteristic of any filler, in terms of both packing density and EMI efficiency, is its geometry or aspect ratio. The aspect ratio of a particle is defined usually as the ratio of the longest dimension to the shortest dimension: for short fibers is the length over diameter (L/D), and for flakes is the mean diameter over thickness (D/T) [6].

Davenport [6] concluded that electromagnetic effectiveness becomes higher when aspect ratio increases. It is the higher aspect ratio to form the network of conductive easily. But the mechanical property of products will decrease as the content of filler increases. Carmona, Barreau, Delhaes, and Canet [6] proposed a geometric scaling law with which the fitted data obtained a dispersion of carbon fibers in an epoxy matrix. They concluded that for sufficiently large aspect ratio, critical concentration (ϕ^*) is inversely proportional to the square of aspect ratio (AR)

$$\phi^* \propto (1/AR)^2 \quad (1)$$

Thus the larger aspect ratio number is, the smaller critical concentration of aluminum flakes reaches the same level of conductivity.

J. Martinsson and J.L. White [7] provided an ABS (Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene) polymer filling with aluminum flakes by injection molding, the aluminum flake was generally orientated with its major axis in the direction of flow. The electrical anisotropy of electromagnetic interference composite is caused by the orientation of flake during molding. The neighborhood of the gate was found to possess unusually high particulate conditions. The abnormally high concentrations of aluminum flakes near gate are consistent with the mechanism of the observed pressure fluctuation. This phenomena conduces to the segregation of aluminum flakes when injection molding. B. Terselius, Y. Sjonell, and J. Jansson [9] reported that a large orientation of fiber was found at mold gate region. It was probably created when the melt flows through the narrow gate.

From above literature review, higher aspect ratio of aluminum flakes can increase conductive effectiveness, but the orientation, fracture, and segregation phenomena of aluminum flakes during injection molding need to be solved to improve its mechanical properties while maintaining the EMI shielding effectiveness. Three aspect ratio value of aluminum flakes (AR6, AR156, and AR695) were used in the experimental for comparing the EMI effectiveness of injection molding products.

EXPERIMENTAL

Three kind of conductive plastics composite material were used in this paper for comparing the EMI effectiveness. The first conductive plastics material is AR6 and content is ABS/AL 37wt% that was produced by a local company, Alotex Polymer Alloy Company in Taiwan. The other two conductive plastics materials are AR156 and AR695 that were produced in the laboratory at the National Taiwan University (NTU), each content is ABS/AL 10.4wt% and ABS/AL 36wt%, respectively.

The model MPL2000 injection molding machine made by the Outstanding Company in Taiwan was used in this research. A steel mold was fabricated with a set of specimen mold cavities of tensile, impact, and electromagnetic shielding effectiveness test specimens as specified in the ASTM standards: ASTM D638, ASTM D256, and ASTM D4935-89. Fig. 1 shows the EMI shielding effectiveness test disk according the ASTM standard. After injection molding process, these electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness specimens were tested at the Industry Technology Research Institute of Measurement Center, tensile and impact specimens were measured at the National Taiwan University.

The electromagnetic shielding effectiveness method adopted in this paper is the ASTM D4935-89 coaxial transmission test that uses a two-piece calibration sample and a corresponding solid test disk. These two samples as shown in Fig. 1 must be of equal thickness and maintained at a high degrees of flatness. This technique is valid over the range of 0.03GHz to 1.5GHz. The test, shown schematically in Fig. 2, requires the reference sample at the right hand side first be evaluated and the received power be recorded as baseline value. This was accomplished by clamping the reference sample between the two halves of the sample holder, attaching the coaxial cables and supplying a sinusoidal signal to one side of sample holder, while measuring the received power at the other side of the holder. This through transmission approach can be modified using the same apparatus to give an indication of the component of the total shield attenuation that can be attributed to each of reflection and absorption. By attaching the receiving side of the coaxial cable to a second connector on the same side of the specimen holder as the input coaxial cable, a measure of the reflected power can be obtained.

Fig. 1: Electromagnetic shielding effectiveness test disk

Table 1: Impact data of ABS plastic of unfilled aluminum flakes

Impact specimens	ΔE (J)	$\Delta E / L$ (J / m)
I 10101	Failed	Failed
I 10102	1.882	148.20
I 10203	2.061	162.30
I 10104	2.181	171.90
I 10105	1.862	146.61
I 10106	2.072	163.17

Table 2: Impact data of ABS plastic of filled aluminum flakes

Impact specimens	ΔE (J)	$\Delta E / L$ (J / m)
I 20101	0.335	26.40
I 20102	0.323	25.44
I 20103	0.321	25.28
I 20104	0.358	28.17
I 20105	0.331	26.08

Fig. 2: ASTM D4935-89 coaxial transmission test for EMI value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental tests were made for tensile, impact, electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness. The first test material is AR6 conductive plastics composite material with ABS/AL 37wt%. Because of low aluminum flake aspect ratio, the value of electromagnetic shielding effectiveness is too low for industrial applications. As shown in Fig. 3, the aluminum flakes were cut to chip formation by screw when compounding. Consequently, the low aspect ratio made its length not enough to form the network of conductivity. The tensile strength is about 70% ABS plastic of unfilled aluminum flakes, and the impact strength is about 20% ABS plastic of unfilled aluminum flakes as shown Tables 1-2. The interface between aluminum flakes and ABS polymer form crack effect in interior. The low tensile and impact strength for the ABS filled with aluminum flakes were obtained in the experiment due to the molecular chain strength and cluster were destroyed at some region to make strength lower than the unfilled ABS plastic. Orientation flow and undispersive problem of the filled aluminum flakes may affect the mechanical property too.

The other two conductive plastics composite materials, AR156 and AR695 that were produced at NTU, each with content as ABS/AL 10.4wt% and ABS/AL 36wt%. The EMI shielding effectiveness values for AR156 material is too low for industrial applications as shown in Fig. 4. The aspect ratio of AR156 should be enough to form a network of conductivity. But the volume critical concentration of aluminum flakes cannot reach packing

fraction that is needed to form network of conductivity. The flow of aluminum flakes was dragged by molten ABS polymer to generate orientation phenomena that decrease aluminum flakes of overlap or conductivity network of formation percent. EMI shielding effectiveness was also affected by mold geometry that easily cause distortion or entanglement of aluminum flakes.

Fig. 3: Microstructure photos of distorted and undispersive aluminum flakes in ploymer after injection process of AR6 conductive plastics (mag.: 200 ×)

Fig. 4: Electromagnetic shielding effectiveness cover of filled aluminum flakes of conductive polymer (AR156)

The final test material is AR695 with content of ABS/AL 36wt%. The aluminum flake is 12.5 mm length, 2 mm width, and 18 μm thickness. Fig. 5 shows the EMI shielding effectiveness values locating between 45 dB and 28 dB for injection molding specimen of AR695 material. The high aspect ratio and enough volume of aluminum flakes in polymer successfully form a network of conductivity as shown in Fig. 6. However, as shown in Fig. 6, the dispersive problem still needs to be improved by considering the injection mold of gate system, runner system, and mold cavity shape in the next step of this project. If aluminum flakes can be dispersive in ABS polymer, the conductive network will be formed in internal of electronic device cases. The electromagnetic interference function is then obtained.

At the current stage, conductive plastic with high aspect ratio of aluminum flakes, such as AR695 material was produced at NTU and its EMI shielding effectiveness values were obtained close to the industrial demands. By the above modified methods of mold and injection process, electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness is expected to meet the industrial needs in the near future.

Fig. 5: Electromagnetic shielding effectiveness cover of filled aluminum flakes of conductive polymer (AR695)

Fig. 6: Microstructure photo of connected network by aluminum flakes in polymer after injection process of AR695 conductive plastics (mag. : 50 ×)

CONCLUSION

This paper is to compare three aspect-ratio conductive plastic composite materials based on ABS compounded with aluminum flakes for the shielding effectiveness of injection molding products against EMI. The EMI values were obtained between 45 dB and 28 dB for AR695 conductive plastics. Some conclusions can be drawn as follows:

1. The effects of aspect ratio of aluminum flakes in polymer is obviously important to form an internal network of conductivity for injection molding products against electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness.
2. The volume critical concentration of aluminum flakes is an imperative factor to form a conductive network for electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness.
3. EMI shielding effectiveness was also affected by mold geometry that easily cause distortion or entanglement of aluminum flakes.

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